

PREDICTING HARD LANDINGS IN COMMERCIAL FLIGHTS DURING APPROACH PHASE WITH E-PILOTS

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ABSTRACT

More than half of all commercial aircraft operation accidents could have been prevented by executing a go around. Making timely decision to execute a go-around manoeuvre can potentially reduce overall aviation industry accident rate. In this paper, we describe a cockpit-deployable machine learning system to support flight crew go-around decision-making based on the prediction of a hard landing event.

This work presents a hybrid approach for hard landing prediction that uses features modelling temporal dependencies of aircraft variables as inputs to a neural network. Based on a large dataset of 58177 commercial flights, the results show that our approach has 85% of average sensitivity with 74% of average specificity at the go-around point. It follows that our approach is a cockpit-deployable recommendation system that outperforms existing approaches.

1. INTRODUCTION

BETWEEN 2008-2017, 49% of fatal accidents involving commercial jet worldwide occurred during final approach and landing, and this statistic has not changed in several decades [1]. A

considerable proportion of approach and landing accidents/incidents involved runway excursions, which has been identified as one of the top safety concerns shared by European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) member states [2], as well as US National Transportation Safety Board and US Federal Aviation Administration [3].

According to EASA [2], there are several known precursors to runway excursions during landing. These include unstable approach, hard landing, abnormal attitude or bounce at landing, aircraft lateral deviations at high speed on the ground, and short rolling distance at landing. Some precursors can occur in isolation, but they can also cause the other precursors, with unstable approach being the predominant one. Boeing reported that whilst only 3% of approaches in commercial aircraft operation met the criteria of an unstable approach, 97% of them continued to landing rather than executing a go-around [4]. A study conducted by Blajev and Curtis [5] found that 83% of runway excursion accidents in their 16-year analysis period could have been avoided by a go-around decision. Therefore, making timely decision to execute a go-around manoeuvre could therefore potentially reduce the overall aviation industry accident rate [4].

A go-around occurs when the flight crew makes the decision not to continue an approach or a landing, and follows procedures to conduct another approach or to divert to another airport. Go-around decision can be made by either flight crew members, and can be executed at any point from the final approach fix point to wheels touching down the runway (but prior to activation of brakes, spoilers, or thrust reversers). In addition to unstable approaches, traffic, blocked runway, or adverse weather conditions are other reasons for a go-around. Despite a clear policy and training on go-around policies in most airlines, operational data show that flight crew decision-making process in deciding for a go-around could be influenced by many other factors. These include fatigue, flight schedule pressure, time pressure, excessive a head-down work, incorrect anticipation of aircraft deceleration, visual illusions, organizational policy/culture, inadequate training or practice, excessive confidence in the ability to stabilize approach, and Crew Resource Management issues [5]. It is for these reasons that on-board real time performance monitoring and alerting systems that could assist the flight crew with the landing/go-around decision are needed [5], [6].

Such on-board systems could utilize the huge and ever increasing amount of data collected from aircraft systems and the exponential advances in machine learning methods and artificial intelligence. EASA is anticipating a huge impact of machine learning on aviation, including

helping the crew to take decisions in particular in high workload circumstances (e.g. go-around, or diversion [7]. Artificial Intelligence in aviation is considered one of the strategic priorities in the European Plan for Aviation Safety 2020-2024 [8].

Under the hypothesis that a hard-landing (HL) occurrence has precursors and, thus, it can be predicted, this paper presents a cockpit deployable machine learning system to predict hard landings considering the aircraft dynamics and configuration. In particular, this paper evaluates three main hypothesis. A primary hypothesis is to assess to what extent HL can be predicted at DH for go-around recommendation from the analysis of the variables recorded from FMS. A second hypothesis is to analyze if precursors are particular to aircraft types. A third hypothesis is to validate if the variability on the aircraft state variables can provide enough information to predict a HL regardless of the operational context (like environmental conditions and automation factors).

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Pilot operating characteristics analysis of long landing based on flight QAR data,”

Long landing events make up the largest percentage of all exceedance incidents and multiply the risk of runway excursions in landing phase. For the aim of exploring operating factors causing long landing, this study examined the pilot operating characteristics of long landing events by the methods of variance analysis, regression modeling and flare operation analysis based

on flight QAR data. Finally it concluded that flare is the most critical operation in landing, which determining the touchdown distance by two key factors of flare time and flare height. Both of the control column and throttle operation plays an important role in the flare process. Pilots' faster pulling up columns and softer throttle closing is probably helpful for a successful flare. In addition, pilots need to control the aircraft to an appropriate groundspeed and descent rate before descending to the flare initial point. The conclusions are expected to be applied into practice to prevent the happening of long landing events.

“Anomaly detection via a Gaussian mixture model for flight operation and safety monitoring,”

Safety is key to civil aviation. To further improve its already respectable safety records, the airline industry is transitioning towards a proactive approach which anticipates and mitigates risks before incidents occur. This approach requires continuous monitoring and analysis of flight operations; however, modern aircraft systems have become increasingly complex to a degree that traditional analytical methods have reached their limits – the current methods in use can only detect ‘hazardous’ behaviors on a pre-defined list; they will miss important risks that are unlisted or unknown. This paper presents a novel approach to apply data mining in flight data analysis allowing airline safety experts to identify latent risks from daily operations without specifying what to look for in advance. In this approach, we apply a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) based clustering to digital flight data in order to

detect flights with unusual data patterns. These flights may indicate an increased level of risks under the assumption that normal flights share common patterns, while anomalies do not. Safety experts can then review these flights in detail to identify risks, if any. Compared with other data-driven methods to monitor flight operations, this approach, referred to as ClusterAD-DataSample, can (1) better establish the norm by automatically recognizing multiple typical patterns of flight operations, and (2) pinpoint which part of a detected flight is abnormal. Evaluation of ClusterAD-DataSample was performed on two sets of A320 flight data of real-world airline operations; results showed that ClusterAD-DataSample was able to detect abnormal flights with elevated risks, which make it a promising tool for airline operators to identify early signs of safety degradation even if the criteria are unknown a priori.

“Real-time flight trajectory generation applicable to emergency landing approach

Flight management systems have greatly reduced cockpit workloads, but are not capable of calculating new flight plans in real time when flight characteristics vary or when flight trajectories become nonstationary. This paper presents a real-time flight trajectory generator (R-FTG) applicable to emergency landing approaches. First, the R-FTG calculates a preliminary flight path, which consists of an initial turn, a straight-line flight, and a terminal turn. The R-FTG then optimizes the preliminary flight path by using a direct collocation method. In order to give the direct collocation method real-time

performance, an idea called stage division is incorporated. Combining the direct collocation and stage division enables real-time generation of near optimal flight trajectories. Additionally, wind effects are considered in the generating process. The R-FTG is evaluated by numerical simulations; calculation results of the R-FTG are compared with those of an offline optimization method, and the calculation results under different bank angle constraints are examined. The calculations for the wind effects are also studied. These results show the effectiveness of the proposed real-time flight trajectory generator.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

A Hard Landing (HL) is a phenomenon in which the airplane has an excessive impact on the ground at the moment of landing. This impact is directly related to the vertical (or normal) acceleration, therefore, HL can be defined as flights where the vertical acceleration exceeds the limited value of the aircraft type during the landing phase. A threshold on such normal acceleration (Airbus uses vertical acceleration $> 2G$ at Touch Down, TD) triggers maintenance requirement, so that can be considered as a criterion for HL detection.

Under the former definition of HL, existing approaches for HL prediction can be split into two groups: those based on a classifier to discriminate flights with normal acceleration at TD above a given threshold from other flights and those based on a regressor that predicts the normal

acceleration with the aim of using this predicted value as the HL detector.

Classifiers can be categorized into machine learning and deep learning approaches. Machine learning methods [17]– [19] apply a classifier to UAV flight data recorded using the Quick Access Recorder (QAR) sampled at a discrete set of heights that define the feature space. Most methods [17], [19] use the values of variables describing aircraft dynamics sampled between 9 and 2 meters before TD. Others, like [18], use statistical descriptors (panel data) of such variables also sampled at the very last meters before TD. On one hand, it is not clear what is the capability of these approaches to capture time-sequence dependencies that variables might have across the approach phase. On the other hand, the temporal window (9-2 meters before landing) used for predictions in UAV flights might not be appropriate for HL predictions in commercial flights. The approximate limit altitude (known as Decision Height -DH-) in commercial flights to decide a go around is 100 feet (38 meters). Thus, regardless of their accuracy in predicting HL, these ML methods are not applicable for commercial flights due to the altitude range required.

Deep learning approaches are mainly based on Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Network (LSTM) architectures. Proposed by [20], these networks are a variant of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) [21] able to model long term dependencies within temporal data. In particular, the very recent work in [22] used

the signals of 3 kinds of landing related features (aircraft dynamics, atmospheric environment, and pilot operations) as inputs to a LSTM network predicting HL. Their comparison to classic machine learning approaches in terms of precision and recall of HL events of A320 flights indicates a potentially higher performance in terms of HL recall with 70% of HL detection while keeping with a percentage (76%) of precision similar to the one obtained by classic machine learning approaches. Despite the promising results, we consider that the experimental design of [22] lacks in some aspects for properly assessing the potential for deployment in the cockpit. First, the test set used is balanced with almost the same number of HL and non HL cases. However, in a real situation, HL cases are rare events that represent only 3-4% of flights [23]. By balancing the test set, precision might be too optimistic and, even unrealistic.

Disadvantages

- An existing system not implemented Sources of errors and capability for go-around recommendation.
- An existing system not implemented hybrid approach for hard landing prediction that uses features modeling temporal dependencies of aircraft variables as inputs to a neural network.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper presents an analysis of approaches for early prediction of hard-landing events in commercial flights. Unlike previous works, experiments are designed to

analyze to what extend methods can be deployable in the cockpit as goaround recommendation systems. With this final goal, we contribute to the following aspects:

1) Hybrid model with optimized net architecture. We propose a hybrid approach that uses features modeling temporal dependencies of aircraft variables as input to a neural network with an optimized architecture. In order to avoid any bias caused by a lack of convergence of complex models (like LSTM), we use a standard network and model potential temporal dependencies associated with unstable approaches as the variability of different types of aircraft variables at a selected set of altitudes. The concatenation of such variability for variables categorized into 4 main types (physical, actuator, pilot operations and all of them) are the input features of different architectures in order to determine the optimal subset.

2) Exhaustive comparison to SoA in a large database of commercial flights. A main contribution compared to existing works is that our models have been tested and compared to SoA methods on a large database of Flight Management System (FMS) recorded data of an airline no longer in operation that includes 3 different aircraft models (A319, A320, A321). Results show that the optimal classification network when all variable types are considered achieves an average recall of HL events of 85% with a specificity of 75% in average, which outperforms current LSTM methods found in the literature. Regarding regression networks, our hybrid model performs similarly to LSMT methods with an average

MSE of the order of 10^{-3} in accelerations estimated at TD.

3) Analysis of the performance of classifiers and regressors. With the final goal of developing a cockpit deployable recommendation system we have conducted a study of the performance of classification and regression models in terms of the flight height and different aircraft variables including the impact of automation and pilot manoeuvres. Results on our large dataset of commercial flights, show that although our regression networks performs similarly to SoA methods (with MSE of 10^{-3} in estimations at TD), the accuracy for detecting HL is very poor (46% of sensitivity). This indicates that regression models might not be the most appropriate for the detection of HL events in a cockpit deployable support system.

4) Sources of errors and capability for go-around recommendation. Unlike previous approaches, we analyze the capability of networks for the detection of HL before the decision height, as well as, the influence of the operational context. We have also performed an analysis of the sources of errors, including selection of the best variable type, optimal altitude range used for predictions, biases due to aircraft type and capability of regressors for HL prediction.

Advantages

- The machine learning approach can also be improved in several aspects. Although results appear superior to existing methods, our models would benefit from a more complex analysis of temporal dependencies

using a convolutional neural network to extract deep dependencies.

- In the proposed system, for a cockpit-deployable machine learning system to support flight crew go-around decision, some results regarding the hardware and software requirements, especially for the speed of networks should be investigated.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as

Login, Browse Flight Landing Data Sets and Train & Test, View Flight Landing Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Flight Landing Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Flight Landing Type, View Flight Landing Type

Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Flight Landing Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN,PREDICT FLIGHT LANDING TYPE,VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

7. SCREEN SCREENS

Screen1: User Login Page

Screen2: Admin Login Page

Screen3: User Profile Details

Screen4: Registration Page

Screen5: User Page

Screen6: Prediction of Flight Landing Type

Screen7: Browse Flight Landing Data Sets and Train & Test

Screen8: View Flight landing Trained and Test accuracy in bar chart

Screen9: View Flight Landing Type Ratio

Screen10: View Flight landing Type Ratio in Pie chart

Screen11: View Flight landing Type Ratio in Line chart

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The following conclusions can be extracted from the analysis carried out in this paper.

The analysis of automation factors (autopilot, flight director and auto-thrust) suggests that these factors do not have any influence on the probability of a HL event and, thus, it might not be necessary to incorporate them into models. Experiments for the optimization of architectures show that the configurations that achieve higher sensitivity are the ones with the lowest number of neurons. As reported in the literature [24] increasing the number of layers and neurons does not improve the performance of neither classifiers nor regressors.

Models using only Physical variables achieve an average recall of 94% with a specificity of 86% and outperform state-of-the-art LSTM methods. This brings confidence into the model for early prediction of HL in a cockpit deployable system. Regarding capability for go-around recommendation before DH, even if we perform better than existing methods, there is a significant drop in recall and specificity

due to the dynamic nature of a landing approach and factors influencing HL close to TD.

Comparing classifiers and regression approaches, experiments show that a low MSE error in estimation of max G does not guarantee accurate HL predictions. Experiments for assessing the capability of models for early detection of HL show that classifiers are able to accurately predict HL before DH. This is not the case of regressors, which predict max G more accurately if data close to TD is considered into the model. The study suggests that classifiers are a better approach for early prediction of hard landing.

Neural networks performance could be increased if they were used to extract deep learning features from continuous signals by using one dimensional convolutional networks and different architectures for a better combination of the three categories of variables. Also, models should incorporate additional parameters such as aircraft mass and centre of gravity position which are known to impact vehicle dynamics.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

Finally, there are some issues that have not been covered in this work, that remain as future work, and should be further developed. Among such cases, stand out the robustness of the classifier (regressor) to unseen cases and its behavior under a drifting data environment. In a safety demanding environment as aviation, it surely be needed to investigate such issues

and we expect to do in further works. In the future, such a system could be expanded to also include Air Traffic Management in which the information is shared with the Air Traffic Controller in order to anticipate the likely scenario and optimize runway use.

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